

DETERMINATION OF PARACHOR IN SOLUTION. PART II PARACHOR OF INORGANIC SALTS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION.

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Parachors of some simple inorganic salts were determined in solution in order to find out the effect of ionisation, if any, on the parachor values and to establish, if possible, a method for the determination of parachor of compounds which are ionised in solution.

It was found that the parachors gradually increase with the increase of concentration and ultimately become nearly constant at a high concentration. From the results obtained it appears that in the study of inorganic salts in aqueous solution the atomic parachor constants can not be employed but a different set of values for the ions are required.

Parachors of some simple inorganic salts were determined in aqueous solution, in order to find out the effect of ionisation, if any, on the parachor value and to establish, if possible, a method for the determination of parachor of compounds which are ionised in solution.

In the present paper an attempt has been made to determine the parachors of ammonium chloride, ammonium bromide, ammonium nitrate, potassium chloride and potassium iodide in aqueous solution. The surface tension was determined by the method of maximum bubble pressure as in the previous work. The results are given in Tables I—V. The theoretical parachors have been calculated from the atomic constant.

In this connection it may be mentioned that Sugden and Wilkins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1291), published a paper dealing with the parachor of fused salts. They have employed one and the same atomic constant for the combined atom and for the ion of an element, which appears to be somewhat difficult to reconcile with modern atomic theories which imply that positive ions occupy a smaller and negative ions a larger "volume" than the corresponding atoms in a co-valent combination (*cf.* Born, *Z. Physik*, 1920, 1, 45). Mumford and Phillips (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2112), are of opinion that, "although the parachors so calculated are in agreement with the observed values in the case of certain salts of organic bases, the fact that large positive or negative anomalies are found with other similarly constituted salts strongly suggests that the agreement is fortuitous, and due to counterbalancing variations in the volumes of the two ions." Mumford and Phillips calculated the parachor values of the ions of the halogen from the atomic parachors of the rare gases, on the assumption that the radius of similarly constituted atoms and ions is determined by the distribution of the outermost electrons, and is inversely proportional to the effective nuclear charge. Cal-

calculation on this basis, either according to the older Bohr theory or according to the newer wave mechanics (*vide* Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 765) indicates, according to these authors, that the parachor values of the halide ions should, on an average, be 1.46 times those of the atoms of the corresponding rare gases and thus about 1.44 times those of the halogen atoms in non-polar combination. The approximate ionic parachor obtained by the use of this factor, when subtracted from the observed parachor of the fused alkali metal salts, give sensively constant values for the parachors of the different alkali metal ions and from these in turn, the constants for various acidic radicles may be obtained.

It will be observed from the results given in the following tables, that the parachor gradually increases with increase of concentration and ultimately becomes nearly constant. In the case of ammonium salts, the theoretical value of the parachor is reached only with the bromide, while with the chloride and the nitrate the values are about 10 units lower. In the case of potassium chloride and iodide the observed values are found to be about 50 units lower than the calculated values.

The present work is not yet complete but the study of various other salts are under investigation. From the results already obtained and given in this paper, it appears, that in the study of parachor of inorganic salts in aqueous solutions, the atomic parachor constants cannot be employed but a different set of values for the ions are required. In this connection it may be noted that the values for the ions as deduced by Mumford and Phillips (*loc. cit.*) do not agree with the results obtained in the present investigation.

In the following tables, x denotes the mol. fraction of the solute, M_m , the mean molecular weight of the solution, P_m , the mean parachor and P_x , the parachor of the solute. The observations were carried out at the average temperature of about 30°.

TABLE I.
Ammonium chloride in water.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.9971	72.16	18.00	52.62	—
0.006625	1.001	72.11	18.22	52.70	107.3
0.009775	1.002	72.11	18.30	52.97	107.3
0.01113	1.007	72.45	18.39	53.28	110.5
0.01749	1.013	73.91	18.61	53.65	111.6
0.02198	1.017	73.16	18.78	53.99	115.1
0.04871	1.037	73.60	19.73	55.69	115.6
0.05977	1.044	74.30	20.12	56.57	118.6
0.07614	1.054	75.04	20.70	57.79	120.5
0.09915	1.069	75.88	21.52	59.40	121.0

The calculated parachor is 133.6.

TABLE II.

Ammonium bromide in water.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.9971	72.16	18.00	52.62	—
0.009935	1.027	72.06	18.79	53.33	123.8
0.01248	1.035	71.73	19.00	53.46	120.2
0.01565	1.043	73.14	19.25	53.93	136.1
0.02647	1.072	73.76	20.11	54.98	141.7
0.03350	1.093	75.63	20.70	55.86	148.6
0.03923	1.105	75.73	21.15	56.44	149.4
0.04979	1.134	76.23	21.98	57.24	145.4
0.06349	1.167	77.21	22.98	58.39	145.5
0.08132	1.210	78.43	24.51	60.32	147.3
0.1048	1.261	77.50	26.39	62.10	143.1

The calculated parachor is 147.3.

TABLE III.

Ammonium nitrate in water.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P	P_x .
0.0	0.9971	72.16	18.00	52.62	—
0.02997	1.043	70.24	19.86	55.12	135.8
0.03804	1.054	70.34	20.36	55.91	138.8
0.04837	1.069	72.21	21.00	57.28	148.9
0.06187	1.085	73.77	21.84	58.99	155.5
0.07971	1.107	75.43	22.95	61.15	159.6
0.1036	1.133	77.21	24.43	63.87	161.4
0.1363	1.165	79.16	26.45	67.69	163.5
0.1826	1.206	80.63	29.32	72.88	168.6

The calculated parachor is 173.4.

TABLE IV.

Potassium chloride in water.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0·0	0·9974	72·31	18·00	52·62	—
0·01189	1·028	73·90	18·67	53·23	103·5
0·01489	1·036	74·16	18·84	53·35	102·1
0·01866	1·044	74·22	19·05	53·56	105·5
0·02502	1·056	74·50	19·41	53·99	106·7
0·02936	1·070	75·56	19·67	54·20	105·9
0·03134	1·074	75·73	19·78	54·33	106·9
0·03941	1·091	76·47	20·24	54·81	107·8
0·04969	1·114	77·47	20·80	55·38	107·7

The calculated parachor is 164 (10).

TABLE V.

Potassium iodide in water.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0·0	0·9974	72·31	18·00	52·62	—
0·01105	1·076	71·83	19·64	53·19	103·1
0·01386	1·094	72·93	19·98	53·35	105·3
0·02328	1·162	73·05	21·45	53·95	109·4
0·03245	1·204	71·24	22·81	55·03	127·0
0·04114	1·254	72·55	24·09	56·07	136·1
0·05248	1·314	74·27	25·76	57·51	146·0
0·06719	1·393	75·01	27·94	59·05	148·3
0·08642	1·490	74·26	30·78	60·69	145·2

The calculated parachor is 200 (10)

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